

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO

Notification of Ethics Clearance to Conduct Research with Human Participants

Principal Investigator: Meiyappan Nagappan (School of Computer Science)

Student investigator: Felix Wang (School of Computer Science)

Student investigator: Ashu Adhikari (School of Computer Science)

File #: 47934

Title: Measuring the quality of AI-generated code: A User Study.

The Human Research Ethics Board is pleased to inform you this study has been reviewed and given ethics clearance.

Initial Approval Date: 10/31/25 (m/d/y)

University of Waterloo Research Ethics Boards are composed in accordance with, and carry out their functions and operate in a manner consistent with, the institution's guidelines for research with human participants, the Tri-Council Policy Statement for the Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans (TCPS2 2022), the Ontario Personal Health Information Protection Act (PHIPA), and all laws and regulations of the province of Ontario (as applicable). Additionally, CREB operates in a manner consistent with the International Conference for Harmonization of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH) Guidance E6(R2): Good Clinical Practice, the International Organization for Standardization of Good Clinical Practices (GCP) as set out by ISO 14155 - Clinical investigation of medical devices for human subjects, Part C, Division 5 of the Food and Drug Regulations, Part 4 of the Natural Health Products Regulations, Part 3 of the Medical Devices Regulations. Both Boards are registered with the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services under the Federal Wide Assurance, FWA00021410, and IRB registration number IRB00002419 (HREB) and IRB00007409 (CREB).

Expiry Date: 11/01/26 (m/d/y)

Multi-year research must be renewed at least once every 12 months unless a more frequent review has otherwise been specified. Studies will only be renewed if the renewal report is received and approved before the expiry date. Failure to submit renewal reports will result in the investigators being notified ethics clearance has been suspended and Research Finance being notified the ethics clearance is no longer valid.

Level of review: Delegated Review

Signed on behalf of the Human Research Ethics Board

Asima Naeem, Ethics Advisor, a33naeem@uwaterloo.ca

This above-named study is to be conducted in accordance with the submitted application and the most recently approved versions of all supporting materials.

Documents reviewed and received ethics clearance for use in the study and/or received for information:

file: Course outline - CS 858.pdf

file: Recruit_Email_Script_47934.pdf

file: Information Letter & Consent Form_47934.pdf

file: Screening form.pdf

file: Survey 1.pdf

file: Survey 2 - part 1.pdf

file: Survey 2 - part 2.pdf

file: Feedback Letter_47934.pdf

Approved Protocol Version 2 in Research Ethics System

This is an official document. Retain for your files.

You are responsible for obtaining any additional institutional approvals that might be required to complete this study.